

SEMANTIC FEATURES OF APHORISMS IN TRANSLATION FROM ENGLISH LANGUAGE INTO RUSSIAN

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***Annotation:** The aim of the article is to reveal the semantic features of aphorisms from English into Russian languages. Aphorisms in both languages are analysed carefully and given examples which shows specific features of them.*

***Keywords:** English aphorisms, literature, philosophy, theory.*

Topicality of our article is in world linguistics, it is being crucial to pay an attention semantic and lexical features of aphorisms in translation process.

An aphorism (from Greek ἀφορισμός; *aphorismos*, denoting “delimitation” “distinction”, and “definition”) is a concise, terse, laconic, or memorable expression of a general truth or principle. Aphorisms are often handed down by tradition from generation to generation.¹

It is often based on philosophical, moral and literary principles. To qualify as an aphorism, it is necessary for a statement to contain a truth revealed in a terse manner. Aphoristic statements are quoted in writings as well as in our daily speech. The fact that they contain a truth gives them a universal acceptance. On the contrary to proverbs the origin of wise words belong to an exact person (writer, poet, publicist, philosopher, scientist, statesman and etc.) and retain its individuality.

Aphorisms have always been popular among people, but lately they have become especially relevant. This interest can be explained the fact that the peculiarities of the modern era require concise ways of expressing thought. There is also an increased research interest in the problems of aphorisms, reflected in an increase in the number of scientific publications devoted to their study. Despite the fact that aphorism has existed since ancient times, it does not have a proper theoretical description: existing scientific knowledge and its boundaries are very vague. In world linguistics and literature there is no developed and substantiated theory of aphorisms, which gives

¹https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Online_Etymology_Dictionary

rise to many ambiguities in modern science. Despite the rather active interest of researchers in aphorisms, at the present stage they have not been studied to the proper extent: there is no generally recognized definition and classifications, characteristics and functions have not been identified.

A lot of philosophers, linguists, writers, lexicographers, scientists of various fields have always pondered over the notion of «aphorism». So here given some definitions of the term “aphorism”. According to Ozhegov's Explanatory Dictionary²: An aphorism is a short expressive saying containing a generalizing conclusion. And Dahl 's Explanatory Dictionary: An aphorism (Greek) is a short and clear saying, a rule based on experience and reasoning; a fragmentary, but complete statement in itself. Many of scientists tried to present the essence of this concept in their own understandings. There are many linguistic research works devoted to the study of aphorisms, which set out the concept, essence, definition, meaning of an aphorism. Scientists carry out a clarification of the concepts of aphorism, parody, maxim, winged expression, epigram, saying, apt word, paradox, pun, essay, parable, fable.

In aspect to our problem is necessary to study those scientists, such as: V. F. Rudov refers aphorisms to phraseology, G. L. Permyakov suggests calling proverbs folk aphorisms and states that " there is no the exact terminological meaning of the word 'aphorism'", pay attention to the lack of a clear definition of the aphorism by N. T. Fedorenko and L. I. Sokolskaya. O. A. Rekhlova names the generally accepted characteristics of the aphorism: conciseness, generality, independence from context, sharpness of form³.

In the theory and practice of translation, an aphorism is regarded as a small artistic work, not as a repetitive unity of concise expression of thought. Therefore, aphorisms can be considered completely independent units of language and can be studied independently. Aphorisms express the speaker's thought not only more specifically, but also meaningfully, figuratively, and most importantly - emotionally. The main ways of translating aphorisms is a translation that conveys a given aphorism using lexical means. Some authors also talk about "free", others - about "descriptive translation". Unlike "one-word" and closer to what is called free translation, the semantic content of the aphorism can be conveyed by a variable phrase.

²[https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Dictionary_of_the_Russian_Language_\(Ozhegov\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Dictionary_of_the_Russian_Language_(Ozhegov))

³<https://moluch.ru/archive/400/88638/?ysclid=m2insyd5uk438752169>

Phraseology completely coincides with the phraseological unit of the translation language in direct and figurative meanings. Below, you can see examples in the table 1.

«To be unable to put two words together»	«Двух слов связать не может»
«Money rules the world»	«Деньги правят миром»
«All is not gold that glitters»	«Не всё то золото, что блестит»
«To live under the same roof»	«Жить под одной крышей»

Partial match with the target language. The same figurative meaning is conveyed using a different image, preserving all the other components of the phraseology as it is shown at the table 2.

«Two dogs fight for a bone and the third runs away with it»	«Две собаки дерутся, а третья кость грызет»
«As cross (glum, silky) as a bear»	«Злой, как собака»
«A bird in the hand is worth two in the bush»	«Лучше синица в руках, чем журавль в небе»

The Aphorisms in English and Russian are almost identical. Aphorisms are similar in meaning and structure in both languages. There are also categories of aphorisms.

According to the meaning of aphorism is divided into many types. They are about health, knowledge, wisdom, etiquette, life, love, happiness and etc.

Many aphorisms used in literature break through their literary use and become relevant in their own sense, apart from the original work in which they appeared. These odd sayings are the Russian analogs of well-known English aphorisms.

1. *The ship has sailed – Поезд ушел – The train has gone;*
2. *What goes around, comes around – За что боролись, на то и напоролись – We got shafted by what we were fighting for;*
3. *Walk the walk and talk the talk – Назвался груздем, полезай в кузов – If you call yourself a milk mushroom, go in the basket;*
4. *No use crying over spilled milk – Снявши голову, по волосам не плачут – No use crying over lost hair when your head's been cut off;*
5. *Fortune favors the brave – Волков бояться – в лес не ходить – If you're afraid of wolves, don't go into the forest;⁴*

In conclusion, translation of aphorisms by right, can be considered one of the most difficult aspects of translation. Since it is very difficult to translate what is considered

⁴<https://www.rbth.com/education/330164-21-bizarre-russian-equivalents-of-english-sayings?ysclid=m2qd2q6z63819883437>

the spiritual heritage of the people, part of their culture. The meaning that one person understands seems to be something new for another. Often, in order to reveal the full meaning of a phraseology, it is necessary to find its equivalent in the translation language. However, the real process is not just a search for equivalent language correspondences, but a complex, multifaceted process, which, in addition to the skill and professionalism of the translator, is influenced by many other factors that subsequently affect the quality of translation. A good translator should be familiar with aphorisms have their translation equivalents ready. But do not forget that the meaning of a phraseological expression can have different emotional coloring and differ depending on the context of use. Language and speech are very multifaceted, and many factors and details must be taken into account when translating.

References:

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